

shyproject.eu

Seawater HYdraulic PTO
wave energy converters

Project number: 101147456

Funded by
the European Union

Wave-to-wire numerical model of Wavepiston

D3.2

Project title	Seawater Hydraulic PTO using dynamic passive controller for wave energy converters
Project acronym	SHY
Project starting date	1 April 2024
Project duration	36 months
Call ID	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02
Type of Action	HORIZON-RIA; HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Topic of the Call	Development of innovative power take-off and control systems for wave energy devices
GA no. and type (budget based)	101147456 - HORIZON Lump Sum Grant [HORIZON-AG-LS]
List of beneficiaries with acronyms	Wavepiston AS (WP); Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU); National University of Ireland Maynooth (MU); FibronPipe GesmbH (FP); Julia F. Chozas, Consulting Engineer (JCC); Marine Systems Modelling (MSM); Consorcio Para El Diseño, Construcción, Equipamiento y Explotación de la Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias (PL); LESER GmbH & Co. KG (LS); Applied Renewables Research Ltd (ARR).
Deliverable number and title	D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston
Work package number and title	WP3 Numerical model development
Task number and title	T3.2 Development of wave-to-wire numerical model
Lead organization and Authors	Applied Renewables Research Ltd – Matt Folley
Submission date	17 February 2025
Dissemination level	Public

Revision History

Rev. no.	Issue Date	Purpose of issue incl. description of main changes	Prepared by	Checked by
0.1	11/11/24	First draft	MF	CF
1.0	11/12/24	Release to EU	MF	ST
2.0	17/02/24	Updated format as requested by EU	MF	ST

The Shy project is financed by European Union through the GRANT AGREEMENT no. 101147456 - Horizon Europe call HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02-10 - "Development of innovative power take-off and control systems for wave energy devices"

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

Table of Contents

1. Executive summary	5
2. Introduction	5
2.1. Scope of deliverable.....	5
2.2. Overview	6
3. Structure of wave-to-wire model.....	6
3.1. Data input.....	8
3.2. Solving system dynamics.....	8
3.2.1. ODE solver.....	8
3.2.2. Force calculation.....	9
3.3. Post-processing.....	10
4. Execution of the Wavepiston W2W model.....	12
4.1. Set an input parameter	13
4.2. Get an input parameter	14
4.3. Parametric analysis.....	14
4.4. Parametric optimisation	14
4.5. Generate a power matrix	15
4.6. Analyse a wave climate	16
5. Representations of currently available PTO Configurations	16
5.1. Telescopic pump	17
5.2. PTO Configuration B - Position-based Coulomb Damping (P-CD) control	18
6. Production of additional PTO Configurations	20
7. Public datasets from W2W model.....	21
8. Conclusions.....	21
Appendix A. Template for new PTO Classes	23

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviations	Definitions
PTO	Power-take-off
W2W	Wave-to-wire
ODE	Ordinary differential equation
WEC	Wave energy converter

1. Executive summary

This document outlines the development and implementation of a new Wave-to-Wire (W2W) numerical model of the Wavepiston technology. The new W2W model is designed to support the evaluation of alternative PTO configurations and control strategies. To achieve this, the model was reconstructed using Python, an open-source programming language, replacing the previous MATLAB-based approach. The use of Python ensures that the model is accessible without commercial licensing restrictions, aligning with the open-science principles of the Horizon Europe program. In addition, the model is structured using an object-oriented architecture, which facilitates modularity, enabling the seamless integration of new PTO configurations and control strategies without altering the core structure.

The model uses TOML files for input parameters, making the model simple to use, without the requirement for specific programming or model knowledge. Advanced numerical methods, including Runge-Kutta solvers, are employed to handle system dynamics effectively. Additionally, the W2W model produces detailed datasets and visualizations, supporting comprehensive analysis and optimization of wave energy systems. This includes parametric investigations, the creation of power matrices, and the evaluation of wave climates. Public datasets derived from simulations conducted across seven representative sea states have been made available on Zenodo, fostering collaboration and transparency.

In conclusion, the W2W model demonstrates significant improvements in flexibility, usability, and accessibility. Its open-source design and advanced computational capabilities position it as a valuable tool for advancing the goals of the SHY project, which aims to drive innovation in wave energy conversion technologies while promoting global collaboration.

2. Introduction

2.1. Scope of deliverable

The scope of this deliverable is to describe the implementation of the wave-to-wire (W2W) numerical model of the Wavepiston technology, which is Deliverable 3.2 of the SHY project, financed by the European Union through GRANT AGREEMENT no. 101147456 - Horizon Europe call HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02-10 - "Development of innovative power take-off and control systems for wave energy devices".

2.2. Overview

The Wavepiston wave-to-wire (W2W) model has been revised and updated to support the investigations into alternative control strategies that will be undertaken as part of the SHY project. The original Wavepiston W2W included irregular wave excitation together with linear hydrodynamic coefficients and PTO forces to produce estimates of the system response and power capture. However, this model lacked a suitable level of flexibility for it to be used to investigate alternative PTO configurations and control strategies. To achieve this, a new Wavepiston W2W model was produced, which is:

- Coded in Python.
- Uses an object-orientated approach.
- Uses plain text files to input model parameters.

Python is an open-source programming language and thus does not require any commercial code. Thus, developing the W2W model in Python means that there is no software limitation in third-parties using the software, which makes it ideal for a collaborative project. Using an object-orientated approach to the software structure facilitates the implementation of alternative PTO configurations and/or control strategies as these can be represented as objects that can be directly replaced without having to modify the rest of the code. Finally, the use of plain text input files simplifies the modification of input parameters to the W2W model and thus increases the usability of the model and the range of potential users. These elements of the W2W model are described in more detail in Section 3 of this deliverable.

Section 4 of this deliverable describes how the W2W model is executed, including a description of tools that can be used to undertake parametric investigations or execute the W2W model to generate a power matrix. Some examples of the model output are also provided as an illustration of the type of information available, which can be used to support understanding and analysis for the development of novel PTO configurations and control strategies. Descriptions of the currently modelled PTO configurations are provided in Section **Error! Reference source not found.**, whilst Section 6 describes how additional representations of PTO configurations may be generated. Finally, Section 7 provides details of the public datasets of the W2W model outputs that are being made available in the Zenodo database and Section 8 provides some conclusions on the deliverable.

3. Structure of wave-to-wire model

The overall structure of Wavepiston wave-to-wire (W2W) numerical model is shown in Figure 1. The execution of the W2W model can also be viewed as a process, which is shown in Figure 2. The key change in the implementation of the Wavepiston W2W model from the previous model has been to build the model in Python using an object-orientated approach (the previous model was built in Matlab using a conventional scripted approach). The advantage of building the model in Python is that it is an open-source programming language and so there is no requirement to purchase a proprietary software license to run the model. This means that the model can be run by anyone, which supports the open-science objectives of the Horizon Europe programme. The advantage of using an object-orientated approach to the model is that this facilitates the implementation of alternative control strategies, which can be constructed as separate objects without having to modify the rest of the code. This is a significant advantage when the specific operation of the PTO control is unknown and may vary significantly between configurations. Specifically, this enables the modification of the characteristics of the PTO force without having to make any other changes to the W2W model. It is anticipated that the benefits of this object-orientated approach will further increase as the complexity of the model and PTO control increases.

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavpiston

Figure 1: General structure of Wavpiston wave-to-wire model

Figure 2: Process for running the Wavpiston W2W model

The general structure of the W2W model can be separated into three parts, the first part is shown in the first column, the second part is in the central columns and the third part is shown in the last column. The first part involves data input into the model, whilst the second part involves solving the system dynamics within an

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

internal time-marching loop. Specifically, this loop involves calculating of the forces acting on the system, followed by solving an ordinary differential equation (ODE). The third part involves post-processing of the data, which includes saving and plotting the data. The following sub-sections describe each of the parts in more detail.

3.1. Data input

The data input for the W2W model is in general defined in text files using a simple mark-up language. Specifically, the TOML (Tom's Obvious Mark-up Language) mark-up language is used because of its simplicity and readability (<https://toml.io/en/>). An example of a TOML input text file is shown in Figure 3

```
[Simulation]
duration = 500
time_step = 0.1
ODE_solver = "RK45"
max_step_length = 0.1
ramp_duration = 30.0
relative_tolerance = 0.001
absolute_tolerance = 1e-6

[FFT]
maximum_FFT_freq = 0.5
FFT_window_type = "boxcar"
FFT_window_length = 2048
FFT_window_overlap = 0.0

[Log]
show_progress_bar = true
ignore_mooring_warning = true
```

Figure 3: Example of a TOML input text file used in the W2W model

The W2W model uses three of these TOML text files to define the parameters of the simulations, these three files are a simulation parameters file (an example as shown in Figure 3), a wave parameters file, and a WEC (wave energy converter) parameters file. Although the parameters could have been stored in a single file, separating the input parameters into three files of different general types facilitates running the simulation for different cases. For example, to run a case for a different sea-state but with the same simulation and WEC parameters, then only the wave parameter file needs to be changed. Or more specifically, only the name of the wave parameters file referenced in the code needs to be change. In addition, tools are also provided to change particular values in one of the TOML text files to facilitate parametric investigations as detailed in Section 4 below.

3.2. Solving system dynamics

The system dynamics is solved using a time-marching method, where the state of the system (positions, velocities, pressures, etc.) are solved at each time-step using the current values of the state variables and the system forces before progressing to the next time-step. The ODE solver used to solve the system dynamics and the calculation of the forces are described in the sub-sections below.

3.2.1. ODE solver

The W2W model is based on a state-space representation of its dynamics where the key states are the hydraulic pressure, together with the displacement and velocity of the sail and spine. The system states are solved as an initial value problem using an ordinary differential equation (ODE) solver such as the variable-step Dormand-Prince Runge-Kutta solver. The ODE solver block has been structured to allow different types

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

of solver, as well as parameters for the solver so that changes to the solver can be made without having to modify the code. Specifically, the following parameters for the ODE solver can be controlled by the user

- Type of ODE solver - current options include
 - 'RK45': Explicit Runge-Kutta method of order 5(4) - Dormand-Prince solver. The error is controlled assuming accuracy of the fourth-order method, but steps are taken using the fifth-order accurate formula (local extrapolation is done). A quartic interpolation polynomial is used for the dense output.
 - 'RK23': Explicit Runge-Kutta method of order 3(2). The error is controlled assuming accuracy of the second-order method, but steps are taken using the third-order accurate formula (local extrapolation is done). A cubic Hermite polynomial is used for the dense output.
 - 'DOP853': Explicit Runge-Kutta method of order 8 . Python implementation of the "DOP853" algorithm originally written in Fortran . A 7-th order interpolation polynomial accurate to 7-th order is used for the dense output.
 - 'Radau': Implicit Runge-Kutta method of the Radau IIA family of order 5. The error is controlled with a third-order accurate embedded formula. A cubic polynomial which satisfies the collocation conditions is used for the dense output.
 - 'BDF': Implicit multi-step variable-order (1 to 5) method based on a backward differentiation formula for the derivative approximation. The implementation follows the one described in L. F. Shampine, M. W. Reichelt, "THE MATLAB ODE SUITE", SIAM J. SCI. COMPUTE., Vol. 18, No. 1, pp. 1-22, January 1997. A quasi-constant step scheme is used, and accuracy is enhanced using the NDF modification.
 - 'LSODA': Adams/BDF method with automatic stiffness detection and switching. This is a wrapper of the Fortran solver from ODEPACK.
 - The name of a Class derived from *OdeSolver* which implements the solver - for example, the fourth-order Runge-Kutta solver could be implemented as RK4
- Time-step used to output the state parameters
- Maximum step length that can be used by the solver
- Relative tolerances for the states
- Absolute tolerances for the states
- Initial conditions that the states have at the start of the simulation

3.2.2. Force calculation

In a dynamic system, the system of ordinary differential equations is typically constructed for each degree of freedom using Newton's Second Law. That is:

$$\dot{v} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{\dot{x} = v} F(x, v, t)$$

where x is displacement, v is velocity, M is mass, and $\sum F$ is the sum of all the forces on that degree of freedom. In general, x and v are the state variable, M a system parameter and F depends on the time (through the wave conditions) and the state variables.

The W2W model is constructed so that the force from the hydrodynamics, the moorings, and the PTO are all calculated separately, which facilitates the modification of the PTO control forces, or any of these forces, without having to change the code associated with the other forces. The object-orientated construction of the W2W model is exploited significantly for the calculation of the forces as this allows both the construction of the force term, e.g. the parameters used to define the control strategy, together with the calculation of the force to be included in a single object.

3.3. Post-processing

Post-processing of the data from the W2W model can be considered to consist of two phases. In the first phase the data is processed to provide additional information that may be required for further analysis, whilst in the second phase the data is output for subsequent use by saving into a particular file format or outputting it as a figure/plot.

As noted previously, the ODE solver provides solutions to the states variables that are used to define the dynamics of the system; however, in general there are other variables that are useful for the analysis of the system. Thus, the first phase of processing involves generating additional states for the analysis of the system. For example, the displacement and velocity of the hydraulic PTO cylinder is useful for further analysis but is not defined explicitly as a system state, although it is used implicitly in calculating the PTO forces. However, it can be defined explicitly using the dynamics of the sail and spine, which is done in post-processing, rather than within the simulation, for computational clarity and efficiency.

The Wavepiston W2W model creates outputs for a large number of states, including the potential for generating additional states based on the PTO configuration being modelled (facilitated by the use of an object-orientated model). The table below provides a list of the standard states that are available as output in the model, which enable detailed investigations into the response of the system to be undertaken.

STATE	DESCRIPTION
<code>hydraulic_pressure</code>	Hydraulic pressure applied to the PTO of all the sails
<code>string_surge_position</code>	String position in surge
<code>string_surge_velocity</code>	String velocity in surge
<code>string_surge_acceleration</code>	String acceleration in surge
<code>mooring_force_string_surge</code>	Mooring force in the surge direction applied to the string
<code>wave_elevation_at_sail_00</code>	Wave elevation at location of sail 00
<code>wave_velocity_at_sail_00</code>	Wave surge velocity at location of sail 00
<code>wave_acceleration_at_sail_00</code>	Wave surge acceleration at location of sail 00
<code>sail_00_surge_position</code>	Absolute position of sail 00 in surge
<code>sail_00_surge_velocity</code>	Absolute velocity of sail 00 in surge
<code>sail_00_surge_acceleration</code>	Absolute acceleration of sail 00 in surge
<code>sail_00_relative_velocity</code>	Velocity of sail 00 relative to the wave
<code>sail_00_relative_acceleration</code>	Accn of sail 00 relative to the wave
<code>sail_00_PTO_position</code>	Position of the PTO on sail 00
<code>sail_00_PTO_velocity</code>	Velocity of the PTO on sail 00
<code>sail_00_pump_force</code>	Pump force on sail 00
<code>sail_00_endstop_force</code>	End-stop force on sail 00
<code>sail_00_wave_force</code>	Wave force on sail 00 due to the added mass
<code>sail_00_drag_force</code>	Drag force on sail 00
<code>sail_00_dMa_force</code>	Force due to the change in added mass of sail 00
<code>sail_00_added_mass</code>	Added mass of sail 00
<code>sail_00_mechanical_power</code>	Mechanical power generated by sail 00
<code>sail_00_hydraulic_power</code>	Hydraulic power generated by sail 00
<code>hydraulic_power</code>	Total hydraulic power generated by the string
<code>electrical_power</code>	Total electrical power generated by the string

For each state the following attributes are available, which not only contains the raw time-series data for the appropriate state, but also bulk and spectral parameters, which can also be useful for system analysis.

ATTRIBUTE	DESCRIPTION
<code>name</code>	The name of the state
<code>dt</code>	The time-step length for the data
<code>data</code>	The time-series of the data
<code>mean</code>	The mean value of the time-series data after the ramp time
<code>std</code>	The standard deviation of the time-series data after the ramp time
<code>min</code>	The minimum value of the time-series data after the ramp time
<code>max</code>	The maximum value of the time-series data after the ramp time
<code>Sf</code>	The spectral variance density for the state
<code>freq</code>	The frequencies at which the spectral variance density is calculated
<code>df</code>	The frequency step used in the FFT analysis
<code>fft_window</code>	The name of the FFT window used - the same as the General parameter
<code>m0</code>	The zeroth moment of the spectrum
<code>m1</code>	The first moment of the spectrum
<code>m2</code>	The second moment of the spectrum
<code>mn1</code>	The first negative moment of the spectrum
<code>Tz</code>	The zero-crossing period as extracted from the data
<code>Tz_min</code>	The minimum zero-crossing period used to "de-bounce" the data
<code>min_array</code>	Vector of the minimum values recorded between two zero up-crossing points
<code>max_array</code>	Vector of the maximum values recorded between two zero up-crossing points
<code>npoint</code>	Number of points in the simulation
<code>nramp</code>	Number of points during the ramp
<code>t_ramp</code>	The ramp time for the simulation (data before this time is ignored in the analysis)
<code>ylabel01</code>	The ylabel used for the time-series data
<code>ylabel02</code>	The ylabel used for the spectral data
<code>scale</code>	Used to scale the output for plotting
<code>freq_max</code>	The maximum frequency to include in the spectral plot

In the second phase of post-processing the data may be saved or plotted. A variety of options for saving the data are provided to maximise its utility. These data saving options include:

- A CSV (comma-separated values) file of the time-series of all the system states
- A CSV (comma-separated values) file of the statistics of all the system states
- A NetCDF file of the simulation data (including the system states)
- A Python pickle file of the simulation data (including the system states)

It is anticipated that the first two options, producing CSV files, are useful for anybody that wants to analyse the results of the simulation but is not interested in the details of the simulation. The CSV format is also easy to export into other tools, such as Excel or Matlab, which is expected to facilitate its use. Thus, the CSV format is used to provide the public datasets associated with the W2W numerical model as described in Section 7. The latter two options provide the potential for a more detailed analysis of the simulation but require more knowledge of the structure of the W2W model and are expected to only be used by those involved in the software development.

Each of the states can be plotted to provide more insight into their response. An example of this plot is shown in Figure 4. In addition, Class specific plots can also be produced by making use of the object-orientated

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

characteristics of the model. For example, a plot used for the verification of the pump force is available, which is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Example state graphical output

Figure 5: Example of specific plot to verify pump model

4. Execution of the Wavepiston W2W model

The W2W model can be run in a Python environment using the command shown below, where the three TOML input files are listed in the parameter list of the function.

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

```
SSM = core_ssm.ssm(wec_params_file = 'wec_parameters_PLOCAN_01.txt',
                   wave_params_file = 'wave_parameters_bret.txt',
                   sim_params_file = 'short_simulation_parameters.txt')
```

The output from the execution of the W2W model is contained within a single instance of the `core_ssm` class, which contains all of the simulation parameters and modelling states. This function can also contain additional parameters that control the execution and output of the function. Specifically, Setting the parameter `execute_SSM` to `False` stops the simulation from running but can be run subsequently using the command `SSM.execute()`.

Setting the `save_options` dictionary (a collection of key-value pairs in Python) enables saving of the simulation data. This dictionary contains the following parameters

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION	OPTIONS
<code>SAVE_RESULTS</code>	Defines whether any data files will be generated	True / False
<code>SAVE_ROOT</code>	The root used to define the save filenames	Text string
<code>SAVE_DIRECTORY</code>	Defines the folder where the results are saved	Folder path
<code>CSV_TIME_SERIES_FILE</code>	Defines whether to save a csv file of the output data	True / False
<code>CSV_STATISTICS_FILE</code>	Defines whether to save a csv file of the statistics	True / False
<code>HDF5_FILE</code>	Defines whether to save a NetCDF file of the data	True / False
<code>PICKLE_FILE</code>	Defines whether to save a Python file of the data	True / False

Setting the `plot_options` dictionary enables plotting of the simulation data. This dictionary can contain the specification to plot multiple states, with the following parameters

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION	OPTIONS
<code>PLOT_RESULTS</code>	Defines whether any data is plotted	True / False
<code>PLOT_STATES_TS</code>	Plots time-series of the states specified	List of States
<code>PLOT_STATES_YY</code>	Plots two states on the same time-series data	List of pairs of States
<code>PLOT_STATES_XY</code>	Plot two States against each other	List of pairs of States

Whilst it is possible to execute the W2W model using the command line, in general it is more convenient to run the model through a Python script, which can be used to set and modify the model parameters as required by the user. As such, it is expected that each script will be tailored to fit the requirements of the user. The following functions are also available that can be used for manipulating and running the state-space model. The subsequent sub-sections provide more details on the use of these functions.

FUNCTION	DESCRIPTION
<code>set_parameter</code>	Sets a parameter in an input file
<code>get_parameter</code>	Gets a parameter in an input file
<code>parametric_performance</code>	Runs the core SSM with a parametric variation
<code>parametric_optimisation</code>	Runs the core SSM with optimisation of a parameter
<code>power_matrix</code>	Produces a power matrix for the configuration
<code>climate_analysis</code>	Runs a set of weighted sea-states for the configuration

4.1. Set an input parameter

Usage: `set_parameter (parameter_file, parameter_group, parameter, value, type)`

This function will set the value of a parameter this is defined in the `parameter_group` of a particular `parameter_file`. The type of parameter may be 'float', 'int', or 'text'. The default value is 'float'. An example of use is

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

```
set_parameter(parameter_file = 'wave_parameters_bret.txt',
              parameter_group = 'Wave',
              parameter = 'energy_period',
              value = 10.0,
              type = 'float')
```

The previous value of the parameter is returned by the function.

4.2. Get an input parameter

Usage: `get_parameter(parameter_file, parameter_group, parameter)`

This function will return the value of a parameter this is defined in the `parameter_group` of a particular `parameter_file`. An example of use is

```
get_parameter(parameter_file = 'wave_parameters_bret.txt',
              parameter_group = 'Wave',
              parameter = 'energy_period,')
```

4.3. Parametric analysis

Usage: `parametric_performance (configuration, parameter_in, parameters_out)`

This function will execute the W2W model using the input directory and files defined in the `configuration` dictionary. The parametric changes are defined in `parameter_in` dictionary, with the output parameters in the `parameters_out` list.

The `configuration` dictionary contains four entries.

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>case_dir</code>	The directory where the files are stored
<code>wec_params_file</code>	The file containing the baseline WEC parameters
<code>wave_params_file</code>	The file containing the baseline wave parameters
<code>sim_params_file</code>	The file containing the baseline simulation parameters

The `parameter_in` dictionary contains four entries.

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>parameter_file</code>	The full path to the file containing the parameter that will be varied
<code>group</code>	The group in which the parameter exists
<code>parameter</code>	The name of the parameter
<code>range</code>	The range of values to be simulated as a list

The `parameters_out` list contains a list of dictionaries, each of which contains two entries, where the potential values of these entries is provided in Section 3.3.

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>state</code>	The State that contains the parameter
<code>attribute</code>	The parameter in the state that is output

4.4. Parametric optimisation

Usage: `parametric_optimisation (configuration, solver, parameter_in, parameters_out)`

This function will execute the W2W model using the input directory and files defined in the `configuration` dictionary together with the defined `solver` dictionary. The parameter that is to be optimised is defined in `parameter_in` dictionary, with the parameter that is being maximised defined in the `parameter_out` dictionary.

The `configuration` dictionary contains four entries.

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>case_dir</code>	The directory where the files are stored
<code>wec_params_file</code>	The file containing the baseline WEC parameters
<code>wave_params_file</code>	The file containing the baseline wave parameters
<code>sim_params_file</code>	The file containing the baseline simulation parameters

The `solver` dictionary contains two entries.

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>method</code>	The method used for the optimisation
<code>tolerance</code>	The tolerance on the optimisation

The `parameter_in` dictionary contains three entries.

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>parameter_file</code>	The full path to the file containing the parameter that will be varied
<code>group</code>	The group in which the parameter exists
<code>parameter</code>	The name of the parameter

The `parameter_out` dictionary contains two entries.

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>state</code>	The State that contains the parameter
<code>attribute</code>	The parameter in the state that is output

Currently, the only solver implemented is the 'Brent' solver. 'Bounded' and 'Golden' solvers are also available but require additional specifications of the bounds of the input parameter. These options can be added if it is identified as being required.

4.5. Generate a power matrix

Usage: `power_matrix (configuration, parameters_out)`

This function will execute the W2W model for all of the sea-states defined by a power matrix using the input directory and files defined in the `configuration` dictionary. The `parameters_out` list contains the parameters to output in the matrix. The power matrix is defined in the wave parameters file, using the following parameters

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>Hs_minimum</code>	The minimum significant wave height in the matrix
<code>Hs_maximum</code>	The maximum significant wave height in the matrix
<code>Hs_step</code>	The bin size of the significant wave height
<code>T_minimum</code>	The minimum wave period in the matrix
<code>T_maximum</code>	The maximum wave period in the matrix

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>T_step</code>	The bin size of the wave period
<code>period_type</code>	The type of wave period ('energy_period', 'peak_period')
<code>power_type</code>	The power used in matrix ('electrical_power', 'hydraulic_power')

The `configuration` dictionary contains four entries.

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>case_dir</code>	The directory where the files are stored
<code>wec_params_file</code>	The file containing the baseline WEC parameters
<code>wave_params_file</code>	The file containing the baseline wave parameters
<code>sim_params_file</code>	The file containing the baseline simulation parameters

The `parameters_out` list contains dictionaries, each of which has two entries

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>state</code>	The State that contains the parameter
<code>attribute</code>	The parameter in the state that is output

The four variables are output from the function. These are:

- the mean power capture in each bin,
- the range of wave periods
- the range of significant wave heights
- a dictionary of the parameters defined by the `parameters_out` list

4.6. Analyse a wave climate

Usage: `climate_analysis (configuration, parameters_out)`

This function will execute the W2W model for all of the sea-states defined within the wave file of the `configuration` dictionary and output the parameters in the `parameters_out` list. The mean power based on the weightings for each of the sea-states is also output.

The `configuration` dictionary contains four entries.

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>case_dir</code>	The directory where the files are stored
<code>wec_params_file</code>	The file containing the baseline WEC parameters
<code>wave_params_file</code>	The file containing the baseline wave parameters
<code>sim_params_file</code>	The file containing the baseline simulation parameters

The `parameters_out` list contains dictionaries, each of which has two entries

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
<code>state</code>	The State that contains the parameter
<code>attribute</code>	The parameter in the state that is output

5. Representations of currently available PTO Configurations

5.1. Telescopic pump

The Wavepiston prototype deployed at PLOCAN currently uses two opposing telescopic pumps to extract energy from the relative motion between the sail and spine. The performance using these telescopic pumps provides a baseline against which the PTO configurations and control strategies developed in the SHY project can be compared. Thus, this provides a measure of the increase in performance associated with the SHY project. Within the W2W model the telescopic pump configuration is defined in the Class PTO_Telescopic_Pump_v1x2.

Each telescopic cylinder on the current Wavepiston prototype has three stages, with increasing cylinder areas so that the PTO force increases with the relative position when compressing. The valve arrangement of the telescopic cylinder is such that the force generated always opposes the motion of the cylinder. Thus

Position	Velocity	Force
$L > s + s_0 > l_3$	$v > 0$	$-A_3p$
$l_3 > s + s_0 > l_2$	$v > 0$	$-A_2p$
$l_2 > s + s_0 > 0$	$v > 0$	$-A_1p$
	$v < 0$	0

Where

l_n cylinder extension at the engagement of the n^{th} stage

s_0 cylinder stroke at central position

A_n cylinder area of the n^{th} stage

L Total length of the cylinder

The other cylinder is arranged in the opposite sense so that

Position	Velocity	Force
$-L < x + x_0 < -l_3$	$v < 0$	A_3p
$-l_3 < x + x_0 < -l_2$	$v < 0$	A_2p
$-l_2 < x + x_0 < 0$	$v < 0$	A_1p
	$v > 0$	0

Unfortunately, an instantaneous transition from zero to a finite force when the velocity changes direction means that the system is very stiff and would require extremely short time-steps to resolve successfully. Moreover, it is not an accurate representation of the forces at this transition because of finite valve response times and the compressibility of the working fluid. However, explicitly including these factors in the model is unlikely to reduce the stiffness of the model significantly and developing a simple representative PTO force model is challenging. A common solution, and the solution that is adopted here, is to use a “velocity ramp” around zero velocity where the force is ramped to the actual force linearly between zero and a threshold velocity. With this representation, the telescopic cylinder is shown as a function of position and velocity in Figure 6 and Figure 7 and can be seen to have the desired characteristics.

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

Figure 6: variation of the sum of both pump forces with position where the velocity is greater than the threshold velocity

Figure 7: variation of the sum of both pump forces with velocity

The use of a "velocity ramp" of 0.02 m/s has been found to provide an effective solution to the system stiffness (and requirement for extremely short time-steps), whilst having a minimal impact on the estimated power capture. An example of how the pump force varies with time is shown in Figure 8

Figure 8: Temporal variation of pump force for two opposing telescopic pumps

5.2. PTO Configuration B - Position-based Coulomb Damping (P-CD) control

PTO Configuration B (Position-based Coulomb Damping control) applies a force that acts against the motion of the sail when the sail is moving away from a fixed position. Within the W2W model the PTO Configuration B configuration is defined in the Class `PTO_Pump_v2x3`. As a physical system, the PTO consists of two opposing hydraulic cylinders, which are designed so that they only pump when they are extending and beyond

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

the activation stroke of the pump as shown in Figure 9. The pumps are then actively pumping into the hydraulic circuit until the braking region is reached, when pressure in the pump is still generated, but this is not fed into the hydraulic circuit.

Figure 9. PTO Configuration B stroke definitions for each pump

This representation of the PTO Configuration B includes friction losses in the pump. Thus, the force that is generated is the product of the hydraulic pressure and the pump cross-sectional area plus the friction. When the braking region is reached, it is then assumed that a constant pressure generates a constant braking force, and an additional force is applied if the pump hits the end of its travel.

Figure 10 shows the pump force for the case when the activation stroke (rod length) is 1.5 metre, the power stroke is 1.0 metres, the braking stroke is 0.5 metres, the hydraulic pressure is 60 bar, the braking pressure is 200 bar, and the pump cross-sectional area is 0.01 m^2 (resulting in a PTO force of 60kN and braking force of 200kN). The end-stop force was set to 500kN.

Figure 10: Net PTO force from the two opposing pumps

At position $x=0$, the effect of the position ramp on the pump force can be seen. When the pump engages, the force ramps up over a short distance to model the effect of fluid compressibility. The same ramp can also be seen at the transition from pumping to braking.

Figure 11: Effect of velocity ramp on pump force

Figure 11 shows the effect of the velocity ramp on the pump force. The size of the ramp may be modified to improve the speed of the simulation (avoiding the requirement for very small time-steps), which can be an issue if the force changes very rapidly. An example of how the pump force varies with time is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Temporal variation of pump force for two opposing PTO Configuration B pumps

6. Production of additional PTO Configurations

The W2W model has been constructed to support the representation and implementation of additional PTO Configurations, which includes alternative control strategies. This is achieved through using an object-orientated approach, so that additional PTO configurations can be included in the model simply by creating another implementation of the PTO Super Class, which defines the interfaces with the rest of the W2W model. Moreover, the code is designed so that the Class for each alternative PTO Configuration is contained within a distinct file and so adding an additional PTO configuration does not require any of the model to be modified and simply a single file, which contains the Class implementation, is required to be added to the source code. The process for generation of a new PTO configuration is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Basic process for generating alternative PTO configuration

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

To facilitate the automatic detection of new Classes within the code, the Class and filename should have the same characters and only contain letters, numbers and underscore characters (_); hyphens (-) and spaces should not be used. In addition, the filename should contain only lower-case letters. Although it is not a requirement it is suggested that a PTO Class starts with the letters *PTO* as this makes it easier to identify the files that contain PTO Classes.

A template is provided (see Appendix A) that can be used as the basis for a new PTO configuration Class; however, it is also possible to modify a currently existing Class, ensuring that the Class name and filename are updated appropriately. An example of where a modified version of the Class may be appropriate is where there is only a minor change to the functionality of the PTO configuration such as the modification of the representation of the friction force in the pump.

The code in the new Class can now be modified and/or written so that it has the desired characteristics. Although it is not required it is recommended that the verification function is also modified to provide an appropriate verification of the implementation of the function. The templates have simple examples for the verification; however, these should be updated appropriately depending on the characteristics that is being implemented in the Class.

It is generally good practice to minimise the use of hard-coded parameters, and all parameters should be settable using the configuration text file. Similarly, the Python dictionary, which contains the states in the model, should always be used to identify which state or degree of freedom that is required (as opposed to hard-coding the state).

7. Public datasets from W2W model

To provide the opportunity for third parties (other academics, engineering companies, suppliers, general public, etc.) to review and potentially analyse and use the results of the W2W model. The output from a reference set of seven sea-states that have been designed to provide a reasonable range of conditions in which the system may be expected to operate. These seven sea-states are provided in the Table below.

Sea-state	Significant wave height (m)	Energy period (s)
1	1.0	5.0
2	1.0	7.0
3	2.0	7.0
4	3.5	7.0
5	2.0	9.0
6	4.0	9.0
7	5.0	12.0

Representative sea-states used to generate public datasets

These public datasets are provided within the SHY project space of the Zenodo database, which can be found at the link below.

https://zenodo.org/communities/shy_project

The data from all seven sea-states for each PTO configuration is contained within a single zip file, which is uploaded to the Zenodo database. As the further PTO configurations are investigated, additional datasets that contain data for the new PTO configurations will be uploaded to the Zenodo database when they are available.

8. Conclusions

A new W2W model of the Wavepiston technology that is suitable for the analysis of alternative PTO configurations and control strategies has been developed successfully. It has been possible to develop this

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

model using Python (a freely available programming language), which maximises the accessibility of the model. The use of an object-orientated approach to the construction of the model has also been implemented successfully, which is expected to provide the flexibility required for the modelling of alternative PTO configurations and control strategies as required by the SHY project.

Appendix A. Template for new PTO Classes

Below is the template for a new PTO Class. As a minimum, the lines marked with a dollar sign (\$) need to be updated to correctly represent the new PTO configuration.

```
# -*- coding: utf-8 -*-
"""
A template for a PTO module

@author: Matt Folley
Last updated: 11 November 2024
"""
from core_ssm import Force
import toml
import numpy as np
from time_series_data import time_series_data
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from tools.verification_tools import PlotRelationship

class PTO_my_class(Force):
    """
    A template for a PTO Class - inherited from Force super-Class
    In this template the minimum lines of code that need modification start with the dollar ($) sign
    The remaining code may be removed if not required

    Attributes
    -----
    _dof          a dictionary of the system degrees-of-freedom
    _state        a dictionary of the system states
    _nsail        the number of sails in the system
    F_pump        a vector of the pump forces
    F_endstop     a vector of the endstop forces
    $ my_parameter a parameter that has been extracted from the WEC configuration file

    Methods
    -----
    __init__(Config_file, SSM)
        Instantiates an instance of the Class
    force(x)
        Calculates the forces from all the PTO units based on the system states
    sail_hydraulic_power(position, velocity, pressure)
        Calculate the hydraulic power for a single sail
    get_states(x, t, config)
        Extracts and returns the PTO states as a member of the time_series_data Class
    ReadConfigItem(cfg, group, item, default=0.0, defer_warning=False)
        Reads an item from the configuration file - inherited from super-Class
    """

    def __init__(self, Config_file, SSM):
        """
        Instantiates an instance of the Class

        Parameters
        -----
        Config_file: string
            the WEC parameter file
        SSM: SSM Class object
            a copy of the state-space model at instantiation

        Returns
        -----
        None
        """
```

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

```

# add attributes from super class (nsail, state, dof)
super().__init__(Config_file, SSM)

# load WEC configuration file with PTO parameters
cfg = toml.load(Config_file)

# extract required parameters from configuration file and store within Class instance
$ self.my_parameter = self.ReadConfigItem(cfg, 'PTO', 'my_parameter', default=0.0,
    defer_warning=False)

# do any further parameter pre-processing here if required

def force(self, x):
    """
    Calculates the forces from all the PTO units based on the system states

    Parameters
    -----
    x : float [nstate]
        system state

    Returns
    -----
    float [nstate]
    PTO force

    """
    # extract the string states from the 'x' parameter
    if 'string_surge_velocity' in self._state:
        v_string = x[self._state['string_surge_velocity']]
        x_string = x[self._state['string_surge_position']]
    else:
        v_string = 0
        x_string = 0

    # get the hydraulic pressure
    pressure = x[self._state['hydraulic_pressure']]

    # initialise the PTO force vectors
    F = [0] * len(self._dof)
    self.F_pump = [0] * self._nsail
    self.F_endstop = [0] * self._nsail

    for isail in range(self._nsail):
        # identify the DoF for each sail
        idof = self._dof[f'sail_{isail:02d}_surge']

        # extract the sail's states from the 'x' parameter
        x_sail = x[self._state[f'sail_{isail:02d}_surge_position']]
        v_sail = x[self._state[f'sail_{isail:02d}_surge_velocity']]

        # define relative stroke and velocity
        position = x_sail - x_string
        velocity = v_sail - v_string

        # calculate pump and end stop forces
    $ self.F_pump[isail] =
    $ self.F_endstop[isail] =

        # total force from PTO is the sum of the pump and end-stop forces
        F[idof] = self.F_pump[isail] + self.F_endstop[isail]

        # calculate the PTO force on the string

```

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

```

    if 'string_surge' in self._dof:
        F[self._dof['string_surge']] += -F[idof]

    return F

def sail_hydraulic_power(self, position, velocity, pressure):
    """
    Calculate the hydraulic power for a single sail

    Parameters
    -----
    position : float
        position of a sail's PTO at a specific time.
    velocity : float
        velocity of a sail's PTO at a specific time.
    pressure : float
        pressure in the string at a specific time.

    Returns
    -----
    float
    hydraulic power of the sail's PTO at the specific time

    """
    # this calculates the hydraulic power as a specific moment
    pump_activated = (position * velocity > 0) and (abs(position) < self.s0)
    if pump_activated:
        power =
    else:
        power = 0.0

    return power

def get_states(self, x, t, config):
    """
    extracts and returns the PTO states as a member of the time_series_data Class

    Parameters
    -----
    x : float [nstate, n timestep]
        time-series of the state vector.
    t : float [n timestep]
        time for each time-step.
    config : dictionary
        configuration used to define time_series_data Class.

    Returns
    -----
    state : dictionary of time_series_data Class objects
        states of PTO.

    """
    nstep = len(t)
    pump_force = np.zeros((self._nsail, nstep))
    endstop_force = np.zeros((self._nsail, nstep))
    for istep in range(nstep):
        self.force(x[:, istep])
        pump_force[:, istep] = self.F_pump
        endstop_force[:, istep] = self.F_endstop

    state = {}
    for isail in range(self._nsail):

```

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

```

s_state = f'sail_{isail:02d}_pump_force'
state[s_state] = time_series_data(pump_force[isail,:], name = s_state, config=config)
s_state = f'sail_{isail:02d}_endstop_force'
state[s_state] = time_series_data(endstop_force[isail,:], name = s_state, config=config)

# additional states can be added if these are useful for further analysis

return state

def verify_force(self, x, t, isail):
    """
    Produces plots and data that can be used to verify the force generated by the Class
    It uses data that has been previously generated by a simulation

    This function can be called using (or similar)
        SSM.PTO.verify_force(SSM.solution.y, SSM.solution.t, 0)

    Parameters
    -----
    x : float [nstate, ntimestep]
        time-series of system state
    t : float [ntimestep]
        time for each time-step.
    isail : int
        the sail number to verify

    Returns
    -----
    None

    """

    # calculate pump and endstop force at each time step
    nstep = len(t)
    pump_force = np.zeros(nstep)
    endstop_force = np.zeros(nstep)
    for istep in range(nstep):
        self.force(x[:,istep])
        pump_force[istep] = self.F_pump[isail]
        endstop_force[istep] = self.F_endstop[isail]

    # extract pump position and velocity at each time-step
    if 'string_surge' in self._dof:
        x_PTO = x[self._state[f'sail_{isail:02d}_surge_position'], :] -
x[self._state['string_surge_position'], :]
        v_PTO = x[self._state[f'sail_{isail:02d}_surge_velocity'], :] -
x[self._state['string_surge_velocity'], :]
    else:
        x_PTO = x[self._state[f'sail_{isail:02d}_surge_position'], :]
        v_PTO = x[self._state[f'sail_{isail:02d}_surge_velocity'], :]

    # plot pump and end-stop force for verification
    plt.figure()
    plot_spec = {
        'title': f'Forces on sail {isail:02d}',
        'xlabel': 'Sail position (m)',
        'ylabel': 'Force (kN)',
    }
}
plot_spec['label'] = f'pump force: positive velocity of sail {isail:02d}'
PlotRelationship(x_PTO, pump_force*1e-3, plot_spec, v_PTO > self.v_ramp)
plot_spec['label'] = f'pump force: negative velocity of sail {isail:02d}'
PlotRelationship(x_PTO, pump_force*1e-3, plot_spec, v_PTO < -self.v_ramp)
plot_spec['label'] = f'endstop force: positive velocity of sail {isail:02d}'

```

D3.2 Wave-to-wire model of Wavepiston

```
PlotRelationship(x_PTO, endstop_force*1e-3, plot_spec, v_PTO > self.v_ramp)
plot_spec['label'] = f'endstop force: negative velocity of sail {isail:02d}'
PlotRelationship(x_PTO, endstop_force*1e-3, plot_spec, v_PTO < -self.v_ramp)
```


JULIA F. CHOZAS
CONSULTING ENGINEER

— Marine
— Systems
— Modelling

Seawater HYdraulic PTO
wave energy converters

shyproject.eu

Project number: 101147456

Funded by
the European Union